

Prevalence of Social Skills among Urban Adolescents in West Bengal

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Social skills are undoubtedly significant for adolescents' present academic success and future employability. In the developmental stage, they go through several intra- and interpersonal challenges related to their academic and non-academic areas. They experience unprecedented levels of anxiety, depression, and sometimes self-harming behavior. Empirical research shows that fostering social skills effectively promotes their psychological well-being and academic performance. Present research examined the social skills among the adolescents and sought to explore the prevalence in the urban areas of West Bengal. The researcher selected 100 willing secondary school students (50 boys & 50 girls) from two higher secondary schools in Kolkata, West Bengal. Social skills were measured by applying the Social Skills Scale developed by Uslu and Genç (2021). K-means clustering analysis revealed that the majority of the students possessed moderate to high levels of overall social skill and its dimensions, except verbal communication and conflict resolution, where the majority of the students showed moderate to low levels of social skills. The outcomes of the study raise awareness and highlight the need for developing social skills and creating a supportive environment in secondary schools, as well as initiating programs designed to foster socio-emotional learning, as well as teacher training and professional development to help educators.

Keywords: School-going adolescence, mental health, urban areas of West Bengal, social skills

Adolescents constitute about 103 billion (16%) of the global population (WHO, 2024) while in India, it is estimated to be 253 million (UNICEF, 2024). Adolescence, the transitional phase of life lying between childhood and adulthood, is well-characterised by physical, cognitive, and psychosocial growth. The adolescence stage extends from 10 to 19 years with early (10-13 years), middle (14-15 years), and late (16-19 years) adolescence (Das et al., 2023). As a critical developmental stage, adolescence is marked by profound physical, socio-psychological, emotional, and cognitive changes (Graber & Petersen, 2017; Sawyer et al., 2018; Shearer et al., 2021). During this period, they encounter several challenges and adversities that can significantly affect their capacity to deal with difficulties in their life and overall well-being (García-Alba et al., 2022; Hellström et al., 2021; Osokina et al., 2023).

Recent research highlights that adolescents are facing unprecedented level of anxiety, depression, and self-harming behaviours (Humaira, 2025). A Russian study found that 79% of children and teenagers feel stressed and have difficulty in communicating with others, and need to improve their copying skills (Samokhvalova & Kryukova, 2016). Furthermore, Qualter et al. (2015) found that 70% of adolescents experience loneliness at some

point. The prevalence of mental health issues among teenagers in India was 23.33% in school and 6.46% in the community (Malhotra & Patra, 2014). In West Bengal, adolescents had the highest levels of anxiety (34.76%) (Roy et al., 2018). Further, empirical research showed that lack of social skills can lead to mental health problems, including depression and anxiety (Mittmann et al., 2023) particularly for adolescents. Rahmadhanty et al. (2024) reported that adolescents with an inadequate level of social skills may experience academic anxiety and depressive symptoms, highlighting the importance of social competence. Bala and Monika (2010) reported that students with low social skills exhibited lower levels of communication skills and self-control, as well as poor problem-solving and decision-making abilities. They feel lonely, are associated with some behavioural problems and negative self-thoughts, and are depressed (Romera et al., 2017). In contrast, higher social skills have been associated with better social adjustment and self-efficacy (Bala & Monika, 2022; Dalal & Sarika, 2022; Kumar & Jyoti, 2023). It can improve adolescents' problem-solving abilities among adolescents and mitigate their bullying behaviour (Deniz & Ersoy, 2025). From the academic perspective, social skills were found to develop academic competencies, resulting in good academic success (Gul et al., 2023; Parke et al., 1998; Ray & Elliott, 2006).

Social skills are essential for successful social adaptation and mental health in adolescents (Trombeta, 2022). Social skills are essential throughout life for social functioning, as well as developing and maintaining acceptable connections and reactions in social interactions through effective communication and socio-emotional functions (Beauchamp & Anderson, 2010; Mittmann et al., 2023). Adolescent resilience has been aligned to well-developed social skills, which allow them to form and sustain social support networks, cope with stressful situations, and overcome environmental challenges (Romero et al., 2019). Therefore, social skills are

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important, especially for adolescents, and the present study focuses on these important skills for adolescents in urban areas of West Bengal.

Most definitions of social skills involve effective communication and adaptive relationships with others, and researchers agree that social skills are acquired through certain learned behaviours that are also socially reinforced (Little et al., 2017). According to Gresham et al (2018), social skills are socially learned behaviours that allow people to interact effectively with others while avoiding socially inappropriate responses. Good social skills contribute to academic success, peer acceptance, and overall mental health (Durlak et al., 2015). Social skills encompass a comprehensive range of competencies that enable individuals to interact effectively with others in various social contexts. These include verbal and non-verbal communication, empathy, cooperation, conflict resolution, and emotional regulation (Uslu & Genç, 2021). According to the OECD (2024), these skills can be categorized into key domains such as social cohesion, self-control, and collaboration, each contributing significantly to personal and professional success.

Present Study

Rapid digital transformation and virtual communication in India, including West Bengal, are affecting negatively social relations and interactions among its members, especially in urban areas. Traditional family structure is transferring into a nuclear family, particularly in Kolkata, where adolescents are not getting enough social support and opportunities to engage with their extended family members, resulting in a lack of proper social skills. They are struggling with interpersonal communication skills and self- or emotional management skills. According to a recent study from West Bengal, 79.3% of school- going adolescents (13-18 years) have poor social adaptive functioning skills (Das et al., 2023). However, there are limited studies that have focused on the prevalence of essential levels of social skills among adolescents. Thakur and Sulaiman (2024) conducted a study having 101 teenagers and found that moderate social media use can improve social skills. Banerjee et al. (2024) showed that social skills can improve communication skills among adolescents, but little research has been conducted to determine the level of social skills among them, or how they possess different social skills from which policy documents, programs can be developed. This study seeks to address this gap by examining the current state of social skills among adolescents in Kolkata. Jaglan and Aarti (2023) showed that students from boarding schools have better social skills than students from conventional schools; thus, in the present study, conventional schools from Kolkata were considered.

This study aims to explore in depth this concern, providing a comprehensive assessment of different social skills among Kolkata's adolescents and information that can help in development of personalised educational policies and intervention programs based on their social skills. The study will raise awareness about the need for developing the skills required to create a supportive and welcoming environment in institutions and initiatives that promote socio-emotional learning, as well as teacher training and professional development to assist educators in supporting students in these areas. The study will help to improve academic achievement by incorporating social skills training into pedagogical practices. Students with strong social

skills are more likely to succeed academically and professionally, and investing in their development can benefit both individuals and society.

Method

Participants

In the present study, 100 school-going adolescent students were selected using a purposive sampling technique. Sample details were found in the Table 1.

Table 1.

Socio-demographic Characteristics of the Sample

Characteristics	n(%)	
Gender	Male	50 (50%)
	Female	79 (79%)
Living Arrangement	Own House/Flat	21 (21%)
	Rented	77 (77%)
Nature of family	Nuclear	23 (23%)
	Joint	23 (23%)

The study included an equal number of male (50%) and female (50%) participants, reflecting a gender-balanced sample. For living arrangements, 51% of families resided in their own flats, 28% in their own houses, and 21% in rented accommodations. Lastly, the nature of the family showed that a large majority (77%) lived in nuclear families, while 23% belonged to joint families.

Research Design

This study employed a descriptive survey design with a cross-sectional quantitative approach to understand the prevalence of social skills among school-going adolescents in urban areas of West Bengal. The quantitative approach allowed for number-based analysis of social skills. This cross-sectional design provided a snapshot of adolescents' social skills at one point in time (Sedgwick, 2014).

Measure

A questionnaire was framed that includes demographic questions as well as social skills scale developed by Uslu and Genç (2021) to collect the data.

Social Skills Scale: Social skills of adolescent students were measured using the Social Skills Scale (SSS) developed by Uslu and Genç (2021). The scale is a 5-point Likert-type instrument, where responses range from 1 (*Absolutely Disagree*) to 5 (*Completely Agree*). It consists of 36 items, with total scores ranging from 36 to 180; higher scores indicate higher levels of social skills. The scale covers seven sub-dimensions: social cohesion (7 items), self-control (8 items), verbal communication (5 items), cooperation (5 items), participation (5 items), nonverbal communication (3 items), and conflict resolution (3 items). The Cronbach's alpha internal consistency coefficient for the entire scale was reported as 0.87, while the sub-scales showed reliability coefficients ranging from 0.50 to 0.84.

Ethical Consideration

Permission was obtained from the institutional authorities after explaining the purpose and procedures of the study. Participants were informed about the nature and objectives of the research,

provided written consent, and were assured of confidentiality and privacy. Participation in the study was entirely voluntary.

Data Analysis

Microsoft Excel and Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) were used for data and analysis. Normality of the data was checked using skewness and kurtosis. K-Means Clustering Analysis was conducted to depict the prevalence (Low, Moderate, & High levels of skills) of social skills among adolescents.

Results

Normality

Normality was assessed by examining the absolute values and Z-values of skewness and kurtosis. The skewness and kurtosis values are -0.900 and 2.731, respectively. Both values fall within the

acceptable range for normality ($sk < \pm 2$ & $ku < \pm 7$), indicating that the data distribution does not significantly deviate from normality as per the (Byrne, 2013; Kim, 2013) (see Table 2).

The z-score is calculated by dividing the skewness or kurtosis value by its respective standard error (sk or ku / SE of sk or ku). According to Kim (2013), for small samples ($n < 50$), absolute z-values within ± 1.96 indicate relative normality, while for medium sample sizes ($50 < n < 300$), the threshold is ± 3.29 .

In the current study, the z-value for skewness (Table 2) was calculated as $-0.900/0.241 = 3.73$ and for kurtosis as $2.731/0.478 = 5.71$. In this case, the Z value of skewness and kurtosis (ku) exceeds the range at ± 3.32 for a medium sample size. However, from the perspective of the absolute Z-score, the distribution still appears to be relatively normally distributed (Kim, 2013). Figure 4.1 further depicts the score distribution, which appears slightly skewed.

Table 2
Absolute Values and Z value of Skewness and Kurtosis of the Variables under Study

Variable	sk	Z of sk	ku	Z of ku
Social skills	-0.900	$-0.900/0.241 = 3.73$	2.731	$2.731/0.478 = 5.71$

Figure 1

Social Skills Scores Distribution (N=100)

Descriptive Statistics of the Study Variables

Descriptive statistics, i.e., mean, median, standard error of mean, standard deviation, skewness, and kurtosis were calculated (Table 3).

The descriptive statistics results revealed the mean, standard deviation (SD), standard error (SE), skewness, and kurtosis of the social skill scores and their dimensions. As shown in Table 3, the average overall social skill score of the adolescents was $M = 117.70$, with a standard deviation of $SD = 14.87$. According to coefficient of variation (CV) rule of thumb, a CV greater than 1 indicates high variation, while a CV less than 1 reflects low variation. The CV was calculated as: $CV = SD/M = 14.87/117.70 = 0.126$.

Since the CV is less than 1, it indicates low variation in the distribution of social skill scores. This suggests that the individual scores exhibited low dispersion around the mean, indicating relatively consistent social skill levels among the students.

Table 3
Descriptive Statistics of Social Skills Scale's Scores (N=490)

Scale	Min.	Max	M	Mdn	SD	SE of M	Sk	Ku
Total Social Skills	61	150	117.70	119	14.87	1.487	-0.900	2.731
Social Cohesion	8	35	22.44	23	5.89	0.590	-0.232	-0.154
Self-Control	14	36	26.58	27	4.16	0.416	0.733	1.38
Verbal Communication	7	14	15.02	15	3.87	0.387	-0.071	-0.462
Cooperation	8	24	17.80	18	3.33	0.334	-0.531	0.364
Participation	6	24	18.12	18	3.40	0.340	-0.550	0.930
Non-Verbal Communication	3	15	10.71	11	2.45	0.245	-0.614	0.565
Conflict Resolution	3	13	7.03	6	2.40	0.240	0.606	-0.160

Level of Social Skills among Adolescents

In the present study, the social skills scores were interpreted so that higher scores indicated a higher level of social skills, while lower scores reflected a lower level among adolescents. To categorize the

students based on their social skill levels, a k-means clustering analysis was conducted using SPSS. This data-driven approach ensured an objective classification by eliminating arbitrary cut-off points. The analysis grouped the 100 students into three distinct clusters based on their social skill scores (see Table 4).

Table 4

K-Means Clustering Analysis of Social-skills Scores of Adolescents (N=100)

Variables	Cluster	Percentage of Students	Score Range	Mean score	Interpretation
Overall Social Skill	Cluster 1	28	126-150	133.32	Higher level of social skill
	Cluster 2	62	102-124	115.63	Moderate level of social skill
	Cluster 3	10	61-99	86.80	Lower level of social skill
Social Cohesion	Cluster 1	21	27-35	30.29	Higher level of Social Cohesion
	Cluster 2	62	18-26	22.37	Moderate level of Social Cohesion
	Cluster 3	17	8-17	13	Lower level of Social Cohesion
Self-Control	Cluster 1	30	29-36	30.97	Higher level of Self-Control
	Cluster 2	64	21-28	25.50	Moderate level of Self-Control
	Cluster 3	6	14-20	16.17	Lower level of Self-Control
Verbal Communication (VC)	Cluster 1	17	19-24	20.65	Higher level of VC
	Cluster 2	59	13-18	15.54	Moderate level of VC
	Cluster 3	24	7-12	9.75	Lower level of VC
Cooperation	Cluster 1	32	20-24	21.34	Higher level of Cooperation
	Cluster 2	47	16-19	17.60	Moderate level of Cooperation
	Cluster 3	21	8-15	12.86	Lower level of Cooperation
Participation	Cluster 1	36	20-24	21.58	Higher level of Participation
	Cluster 2	62	12-19	16.47	Moderate level of Participation
	Cluster 3	02	6-8	7	Lower level of Participation
Non-Verbal Communication (NVC)	Cluster 1	41	12-15	12.98	Higher level of NVC
	Cluster 2	49	08-11	9.84	Moderate level of NVC
	Cluster 3	10	03-07	5.70	Lower level of NVC
Conflict Resolution	Cluster 1	16	10-13	11.31	Higher level of Conflict Resolution
	Cluster 2	61	06-09	06.95	Moderate level of Conflict Resolution
	Cluster 3	23	03-05	4.26	Lower level of Conflict Resolution

The cluster analysis (Table 4) revealed three distinct groups of students based on their overall social skill levels: higher, moderate, and lower. The majority of students (62%, $N = 62$) had a moderate level of overall social skill, with a mean score (M) of 115.63. Twenty-eight percent of students (28%, $N = 28$) demonstrated a higher level of social skills, with $M = 133.32$, while 10% of the students (10%, $N = 10$) fell into the lower social skill category, with $M = 86.80$. Aside from overall scores, research also showed three levels (high, moderate, & poor) of several dimensions of social skill.

In terms of social cohesion, 62% of the students (62%, $N = 62$) demonstrated a moderate level, with $M = 22.37$. Twenty-one percent (21%, $N = 21$) exhibited a higher level of social cohesion, with $M = 30.29$, whereas 17% (17%, $N = 17$) displayed a lower level, with $M = 13.00$ (Table 4).

Regarding self-control, the majority of students (64%, $N = 64$) showed a moderate level, with $M = 25.50$. Meanwhile, 30% (30%, $N = 30$) demonstrated a higher level of self-control, with $M = 30.97$, and 6% (6%, $N = 6$) exhibited a lower level, with $M = 16.17$ (Table 4).

For verbal communication, 59% of the students (59%, $N = 59$) demonstrated a moderate level, with $M = 15.54$. Seventeen percent (17%, $N = 17$) displayed a higher level, with $M = 20.65$, while 24%

(24%, $N = 24$) showed a lower level, with $M = 9.75$ (Table 4).

In terms of cooperation, 47% of the students (47%, $N = 47$) exhibited a moderate level, with $M = 17.60$. Thirty-two percent (32%, $N = 32$) displayed a higher level, with $M = 21.34$, and 21% (21%, $N = 21$) showed a lower level, with $M = 12.86$ (Table 4).

The results for participation revealed that 62% of the students (62%, $N = 62$) exhibited a moderate level, with $M = 16.47$, while 36% (36%, $N = 36$) demonstrated a higher level, with $M = 21.58$. Notably, no students were classified in the lower participation category (Table 4).

For non-verbal communication, 49% of the students (49%, $N = 49$) displayed a moderate level, with $M = 9.84$. Forty-one percent (41%, $N = 41$) exhibited a higher level, with $M = 12.98$, whereas 10% (10%, $N = 10$) demonstrated a lower level, with $M = 5.70$ (Table 4).

Finally, in conflict resolution, 61% of the students (61%, $N = 61$) demonstrated a moderate level, with $M = 6.95$. Sixteen percent (16%, $N = 16$) exhibited a higher level, with $M = 11.31$, while 23% (23%, $N = 23$) displayed a lower level, with $M = 4.26$ (Table 4).

Discussion

The findings indicated that the majority of students have moderate

levels of overall social skills, with smaller groups showing higher and lower levels. The study found that 62% of the adolescents had moderate social skills, whereas 28% demonstrated higher and 10% lower levels. These results are supported by the previous study conducted both outside (Alfi et al., 2024; Paroginog et al., 2018) and within India (Rachna, 2018). They reported having a moderate level of social skills. Another study in India showed that majority of the students (83%) have high level of social skills, whereas only 10% have average level and 7% have low level of social skills (Bala & Monika, 2010).

In terms of specific social skills, most students demonstrated high to moderate levels of social cohesion, self-control, cooperation and participation. Adolescence had a significant percentage of people at the lower to moderate level in both dimensions of social skills, namely verbal communication and Conflict resolution. These outcomes might be attributed to academic pressures that have left them with limited time for regular family interaction or family engagement (Chopra et al., 2021; Mayya et al., 2022) but they make the most of their time through peer interaction, in which they have a moderate level of those skills that most students do not have. Other things to keep in mind are that excessive use of digital devices, games, lack of face-to-face communication resulting in restricted conversation and no challenges, may lead to lower levels of verbal communication skills and conflict resolution abilities among adolescents. The findings of the present study, particularly the moderate levels of overall social skills across several domains, reflect the unique socio-cultural characteristics of Kolkata.

Implications of the Study

The findings of this present study have several important implications for educational policies and practices. First, the majority of students had moderate social skills across their dimensions, except in verbal communication and conflict resolution. These outcomes suggest the target-specific interventions focusing on these specific skills domains. Educational initiatives like life skills sessions, collaborative, cooperative learning, project works, conflict resolution workshops, community service programme, etc. should be designed to enhance communication strategies, conflict management, and collaboration skills, fostering overall social competence. The implication of this study encourages educational stakeholders to integrate socio-emotional-educational skills in the course syllabus. Further, teachers should be trained to cultivate and facilitate fostering social skills among students in their regular classroom settings

Limitations and Future Research Practices

The study has several limitations that should be taken into account. The study focused on two schools in Kolkata, which may not fully represent the adolescent population in West Bengal and other parts of India. As a result, the findings may not apply to all adolescents in different cultural, urban, or rural settings, which should be included for future research to ensure robust generalizability. The sample size of the present study was 100 adolescents, which is relatively small, thus limiting the power and reliability of the findings. Future studies should consider a larger sample size to make a more comprehensive conclusion. Moreover, as a cross-sectional research design, the study limits its ability to conclude the development of social skills over time. Data were collected using a self-reported questionnaire, which

is subject to response bias. Incorporating multiple sources of data collection, like parents' assessment, teachers' evaluation, peer assessments, etc., would be more objective measure of social skills.

Despite these limitations, the study having social skills among school-going adolescents initially raises awareness among all the stakeholders, which may lead to further attention for the role of social skills practices in educational policy.

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